

Structural Studies of Biomolecules in the Gas Phase by Chirped-Pulse Fourier Transform Microwave Spectroscopy

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Abstract

Studies of the gas phase structures of biomolecules provide an important connection to theoretical methods for modeling large molecule structure. The key features of biomolecule structures, such as their conformational flexibility and the complexes they form through intermolecular interactions, pose major challenges to spectroscopic techniques. Rotationally resolved spectroscopy holds the possibility of true structure determination where analysis of the spectra of isotopic species provides actual atom positions in the three-dimensional structure. Molecular rotational spectroscopy is ideally suited for this type of study because it offers high spectral resolution and is generally applicable (requiring only a polar molecule). A chirped-pulse Fourier transform microwave (CP-FTMW) spectrometer has been optimized for biomolecule spectroscopy. The sensitivity of this technique makes it possible to perform heavy atom (¹³C, ¹⁵N, ¹⁸O) structure determination using the natural abundance of the isotopes. The performance of the spectrometer is illustrated by obtaining the structure of the phenol dimer, a model system that is a challenge for theoretical methods. For application to larger biomolecule systems, it is expected that rotational spectroscopy alone will face challenges in making structure determinations. The scope of problems that can be addressed by rotational spectroscopy can be expanded through double-resonance spectroscopy approaches that provide a “second dimension” of structural information. A general method to implement laser-microwave double resonance spectroscopy is described. We also discuss the potential for developing low-cost microwave detectors for biomolecule spectroscopy that achieve savings by reducing the measurement bandwidth. This approach is particularly promising for developing low-frequency CP-FTMW spectrometers that are well-suited for large molecule rotational spectroscopy.

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Introduction.

The need for quantitative structural and dynamical information about large molecules remains a driving force for technique development in spectroscopy.¹⁻³ This need is especially critical for large molecules that are biologically relevant. The structure and conformational flexibility of biological molecules plays an important role in their function. In order to model structures of biological molecules, accurate input from theoretical chemistry is needed. The field of gas phase biomolecule spectroscopy has emerged in recent years with the goal of providing stringent tests for different computational methods in structural modeling. In particular, this field has developed high-sensitivity spectroscopic methods that can characterize the structures of molecules large enough to contain information about the through-space intramolecular interactions which define the conformational potential energy surface, or “energy landscape”.⁴⁻⁶ A second important class of structural problems involves the complexation of flexible molecules with other biologically important molecules, such as water, to assess modification of the landscape by intermolecular interactions.⁷⁻¹⁰

There are two major experimental challenges for gas phase biomolecule spectroscopy. First, spectroscopic techniques with high sensitivity are required because the gas phase samples typically have low number density. Many of the successful spectroscopic techniques in this field have used electronic spectroscopy in the ultraviolet (UV) frequency region where laser-induced fluorescence (LIF) detection, or multi-photon ionization followed by mass spectrometric detection, is possible. Structural information can be gleaned from an analysis of the vibronic structure in the electronic spectrum. Additional structural characterization is obtained by performing infrared (IR)-UV double-resonance spectroscopy.¹¹⁻¹⁵ A vibrational spectrum, observed through changes, or dips, in the fluorescence intensity, can provide information about special structural features such as the presence of intramolecular or intermolecular hydrogen bonds through the characteristic shifts of hydride stretch vibrations.

The second major challenge for this field is the development of sources for gas phase biomolecules. The advantages of sample cooling are well established in this field and most studies use pulsed jet molecular beams as first introduced by Smalley, Wharton, and Levy.¹⁶ Ion trapping methods also make use of cooling, achieved in this case through collisional cooling with

a cold buffer gas.¹⁷⁻¹⁸ Apart from ion trapping techniques, the main molecule source used for gas phase biomolecule spectroscopy is pulsed laser ablation. This technology has seen continuous improvement through the effort of several groups in the field.¹⁹⁻²⁵

Rotationally resolved spectroscopies are especially well suited for the characterization of the three-dimensional structure of biomolecules in the gas phase. Rotationally resolved spectra can be measured by pure rotational spectroscopy (in the microwave frequency (MW) range),²⁶⁻²⁷ by ro-vibrational spectroscopy (in the IR),²⁸ or by electronic spectroscopy (in the UV).²⁹⁻³¹ However, only pure rotational spectroscopy and rotationally resolved electronic spectroscopy have achieved the sensitivity for routine application in biomolecule spectroscopy. The three primary parameters determined from the analysis of a rotationally resolved spectrum, the rotational constants (A, B, and C), give direct information about the mass distribution of the molecule. These constants, related to the moments-of-inertia about the three principal rotational axes, can be determined to high precision and can reliably distinguish geometries with small differences. The determination of the conformational structure of *p*-methoxyphenethylamine (*p*MPEA) by high-resolution UV and molecular rotational spectroscopy illustrates this ability.³²⁻³⁴ These high-resolution spectra contain other information that can help determine the three-dimensional structure when coupled with calculations from electronic structure theory. Corroborating information include the relative directions of the transition moments in the principal axis system (obtained from an intensity analysis) and, with sufficient resolution, the nuclear quadrupole hyperfine structure (mainly from ¹⁴N for biomolecules).

Rotationally resolved spectroscopy offers a unique capability that is not routinely exploited: the determination of atom positions through isotopic substitution. The atom positions are independently determined through the changes in the moments-of-inertia accompanying isotopic substitution using the method described by Kraitchman in 1953.³⁵⁻³⁶ Using this procedure (a “Kraitchman analysis”), the three-dimensional structure of the molecule can be built up atom-by-atom. The limitations of this analysis have been the subject of several studies³⁷⁻³⁸ and there are alternate methods of “structure fitting” that can use the isotopic information.³⁹⁻⁴⁰ However, Kraitchman analysis has the advantage of giving atom positions independent of any structural model. Also, the determined positions are not correlated so that

inherent errors of the analysis do not percolate through the structure. Further structure refinement is possible using electronic structure theory to estimate the vibrational effects in the analysis leading to equilibrium structures directly comparable to theoretical calculations.⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ Although there are known difficulties in this analysis, substitution structure determination has the potential to be the most exacting study of gas phase biomolecule structure.

In what follows, we highlight recent developments in broadband molecular rotational spectroscopy that have come about by using chirped-pulse Fourier transform microwave (CP-FTMW) spectroscopy. These include the determination of a heavy-atom (C, N, O) substitution structure of a gas phase biomolecule using the singly-substituted isotopomers (¹³C, ¹⁵N, and ¹⁸O) in natural abundance. Because these isotopomers occur at the 0.2-1% level, this experimental approach clearly makes strong demands on spectrometer sensitivity. Current spectrometer performance is illustrated through the determination of the heavy atom substitution structure of the phenol dimer in natural abundance.

We also discuss related techniques that have the potential to expand the use of microwave spectroscopy as a diagnostic tool for biomolecular structure and to provide additional structural characterization when the rotational spectrum is insufficient to unambiguously determine the structure. The first extension is the development of reduced bandwidth CP-FTMW spectrometers as a low-cost, general purpose detector. The second development is laser-FTMW double-resonance spectroscopy that makes it possible to obtain the spectral signatures of an individual molecular species in a complex sample mixture. Applications of these techniques to biomolecule structure are illustrated by results from the tautomer system of 2-hydroxypyridine and 2-pyridone.

Experimental.

Broadband Chirped Pulse Fourier Transform Microwave Spectrometer

The chirped-pulse Fourier transform microwave (CP-FTMW) spectrometer was first described in 2006⁴⁵ and an updated description of the spectrometer design including the current state-of-the-art high-speed digital electronics has been presented.⁴⁶ A schematic of the spectrometer operating in the 7-18 GHz frequency band is shown in Fig. 1. The CP-FTMW

spectrometer acquires a broadband (11 GHz) spectrum on each signal acquisition and uses the efficiency of chirped-pulse excitation (or rapid passage)⁴⁷ to achieve high-sensitivity with the power levels available in traveling wave tube amplifiers. The measurement sensitivity is determined by the number of averages of the rotational free induction decay (FID), with the noise level dropping as the square root of the number of averages. To obtain high sensitivity it is necessary to average each FID in the time domain.⁴⁸

For biomolecule spectroscopy, where samples may be difficult to obtain and expensive, the spectrometer needs to consume small amounts of sample. The two main strategies we have used for this purpose are to acquire 10 FIDs on each sample injection and to use multiple nozzles for sample injection. The implementation of these methods has been described previously.⁴⁶ When implementing the multiple FID collection, we are required to use a 200 W traveling wave tube amplifier (many of our previous results used a 1 kW amplifier). The lower power amplifier is needed to avoid damage to the PIN diode that protects the low-noise receiver. This diode is rated for 1 μ s pulse durations at 1 kW peak power and each chirped micropulse has meets these specifications. However, the macropulse contains 10 of these pulses in about 250 μ s, and the diode cannot tolerate this load. The separation between the broadcast and receive horn antennas is 1 m and the spectrometer can accommodate three pulsed nozzle sources. Only two were available for the experiments described here.

The current bottleneck in data collection comes from the time required to perform the signal averaging of the FIDs. In standard operation of the spectrometer, we digitize each FID for 20 μ s at 50 Gs/s; with the multiple FID collection, the record length is 10 Mpts for each data acquisition cycle. The repetition rate of the measurement cycle is 0.5 Hz under these conditions. Deep signal averaging requires long measurement times and it is difficult to maintain long-term time stability over the course of the experiment. A new design of the data system by Tektronix is expected to improve the signal processing rate by a factor of 20 or more in the next year.

To increase the signal collection rate, and better approximate performance levels expected by 2012, we have measured the phenol dimer spectrum with reduced bandwidth and have recorded the spectrum in the 7-9 GHz frequency range. The reduced bandwidth allows us

to use a 6.25 Gs/s digitization rate and increases the repetition rate of the spectrometer to 5 Hz. Since 10 FIDs are acquired in each measurement cycle, the effective spectrum averaging rate is 50 Hz. The phenol dimer spectrum reported here is the average of 3.24 M spectra (324,000 measurement cycles) and was acquired in 18 hours. Excellent phase stability is maintained over this short time frame. With future projected gains (20x) in data processing, a spectrum with equal sensitivity can be obtained over the full 11 GHz spectrometer bandwidth in 9 hours.

The sample of phenol (99%) was obtained from Aldrich and used without further purification. The sample was loaded into 1 mm diameter liquid reservoir nozzles⁴⁹ based on the General Valve Series 9 design. The sample was heated to 85°C and a backing pressure of 2 atm of Ne carrier gas was used. We estimate that the 3.24 M FID average spectrum (2 GHz bandwidth) consumed about 1 g of sample.

Reduced Bandwidth CP-FTMW Design

The reduced bandwidth CP-FTMW spectrometer operates on the same principles as the spectrometer described above. The spectrometer design has been described elsewhere.⁵⁰⁻⁵² and is shown in Fig. 2. The major change in operation is the reduction of the chirped-pulse bandwidth to about 500 MHz. This modification offers cost savings by employing lower sampling rates in both the AWG and the digitizer for FID detection. In addition, a lower power solid state microwave amplifier (1 W in the present design, Microwave Power L0618-30, 6-18 GHz) can be used. The use of lower peak power amplifiers gives a slight improvement in spectrometer sensitivity because it reduces the “dead time” required between sample polarization and FID collection. Additional performance gains are achieved by replacing one of the microwave horns by a mirror to improve the cavity Q. The $\sim 1 \mu\text{s}$ chirped (0-250 MHz) pulse is provided by a Tektronix 3252 arbitrary waveform generator (AWG), mixed with the output of an HP 83752B synthesizer, and amplified by the 1 W solid-state amplifier. Next, the pulse travels through a circulator and is broadcast into the cavity by an antenna. The resulting free induction decay (FID) is then collected by the horn, and passed through a switch that protects the low-noise amplifier (Miteq AMF-SF-08001800-14-10P) from the power of the initial microwave pulse. After 20x amplification, the signal is mixed down using the synthesizer frequency, amplified again (Miteq AU-1562, 0.01-500 MHz), and detected using a Tektronix DPO7054 oscilloscope

(500 MHz, 20 Gs/s) where it is signal averaged and Fourier transformed to produce a frequency spectrum.

For the experiments presented here, samples were introduced into the vacuum chamber by passing a backing gas of He or He/Ne over a heated solid sample ($\sim 100^\circ$ C) of 2-hydroxypyridine and expanding the gas mixture using a General Valve Series 9 pulsed nozzle. Digital delay generators triggered and synchronized the nozzle, amplifiers, switches, laser, and oscilloscope. The gas pulse usually lasted from 400-600 μ s and began 700-800 μ s before the pulse from the AWG.

Coherence-Converted Population Transfer (CCPT) Laser-FTMW Spectroscopy

CCPT has its origins in the earlier experiments of Endo and co-workers,⁵³ who showed that a cavity FTMW spectrometer of the Balle-Flygare type⁵⁴ coupled to a tunable pulsed dye laser could be used to obtain MODR spectra of several small free radicals in supersonic jets. The technique has been used to detect both IR and UV absorptions.^{53,55} In the current version of the technique,^{34,56} the FTMW cavity spectrometer is tuned to a microwave transition, and a two-pulse MW sequence is applied. Both pulses have duration 500 ns and are separated by 50 ns. The energy of the first pulse is adjusted to create an optimal pure rotational signal. Then, the second pulse is applied, and its phase and amplitude are set so that it nulls the pure rotational signal as much as possible, creating a “zero-background”. In the Bloch-model picture (see Fig. 3), the first pulse is a “ $\pi/2$ ” pulse, and the second pulse is a “ $-\pi/2$ ” pulse. (The attribution of the pulse as “ $\pi/2$ ” is only approximate because the M_J -dependence of the rotational transition moment precludes a true $\pi/2$ -pulse.)

If a laser pulse is applied that is in near resonance with a transition involving one of the two states being monitored with the FTMW cavity, and if it is timed to fire between the two microwave pulses, it will create a new population difference that will not be nulled by the second microwave pulse. Instead, as shown in Fig. 3, a new coherence will be created that can be detected as a rotational FID. Typically, several FID's (10-100) are averaged per laser step; these are then processed using a MATHCAD program, Fourier transformed, and the imaginary part of the Fourier transform is plotted as a function of laser frequency to generate the absorption

spectrum. By suppressing the effect of shot-to-shot nozzle fluctuation on the signal level, this technique increases the sensitivity of FTMW- detected laser spectroscopy by roughly an order of magnitude. In addition, the phase of the detected coherence provides an automatic assignment of the ground state of the laser-induced transition.

For these experiments, a 10 Hz pulsed dye laser (Lambda Physik ScanMate Pro) was employed. The dye laser was equipped with a β -barium borate doubling crystal; typical pulse energies at 280 nm were 7mJ/pulse. The laser beam was expanded to about 4 cm, to ensure good overlap with the beam waist of the microwave spectrometer.

Results.

Substitution Structure of the Phenol Dimer

To illustrate the sensitivity achieved by broadband CP-FTMW spectroscopy, we present an initial analysis of the phenol dimer structure. This molecule is an important benchmark for electronic structure calculations because it has “mixed” interactions that compete to define the structure.⁵⁷ One interaction is the electrostatic hydrogen bonding interaction between the O-H groups of the phenol monomers. The second interaction comes from dispersion forces mainly involving the two aromatic rings. The balance between these interactions is important for setting the “hinge” angle of the dimer, defined as the C1-O1-O2-C7 dihedral angle, and this aspect of the structure will be the primary focus of the discussion. The phenol dimer also provides a comparison to rotationally-resolved electronic spectroscopy techniques, where the spectrum has been investigated by both time-domain rotationally-resolved spectroscopy (rotational coherence spectroscopy)⁵⁸⁻⁵⁹ and high-resolution, frequency-domain spectroscopy.⁶⁰ A more complete analysis of the rotational spectrum and structure will be presented in a separate publication.

The CP-FTMW spectrum of phenol dimer is shown in Figs. 4 and 5. Panel A of Fig. 4 shows a 2 GHz region of the pure rotational spectrum where the strongest transitions belong to the phenol monomer. The dimer spectrum is about 10 times weaker and it is compared to the calculated spectrum shown beneath the experimental spectrum. The spectrum is shown on an expanded scale in panel B. In both figures, the simulated spectrum of the phenol dimer was

generated using SPCAT⁶¹ to show the relative intensity accuracy achieved by CP-FTMW spectroscopy. The pure rotational spectrum of the phenol dimer was immediately assignable because the previous work provided accurate values for the rotational constants. The results for fitting the observed spectrum to the Watson asymmetric top Hamiltonian are given in Table 1 where the rotational constants are compared to the previous values. The high resolution of pulsed jet microwave spectroscopy produces significant improvement in the determination of the molecular constants.

The major advance enabled by CP-FTMW spectroscopy is sufficient sensitivity to obtain the pure rotational spectra of the heavy atom isotopomers (¹³C and ¹⁸O) of the phenol dimer in natural abundance. The ¹³C isotopic satellites are shown in Fig. 5 for the $14_1 14 - 13_1 13$ (J_{KaKc} labels) pure rotational transition of the phenol dimer at 8198.28 MHz, indicated by the asterisk in panel A. Panel B expands the vertical scale by a factor of 100, the natural abundance factor for ¹³C. To highlight the isotopic satellite pattern, a masked spectrum that shows only the assigned transitions is shown below the experimental spectrum (the shifts induced by the ¹⁸O isotopomers, where there is a 2 u mass change, are beyond the region shown here). The isotopomer transitions come in pairs because there is near symmetry in the aromatic rings for the phenol dimer. Even with this structural feature, the CP-FTMW spectrum fully resolves all of the isotopomer transitions.

The heavy atom substitution structure of the phenol dimer is shown in Fig. 6. One potential difficulty with using isotopic substitution for structure determination is that the Kraitchman analysis only returns the magnitude of the coordinates of each atom in the principal axis system. For phenol dimer, an examination of the expected isotopic pattern based on calculated structures showed that in each ¹³C pair the carbon associated with the acceptor ring has the lower frequency rotational transition. This effect was used to set the relative signs of the substitution coordinates and to generate the final structure. The experimental hinge angle from the substitution structure is 66°. This is in close agreement with values determined in previous studies (59-63°).

The experimental structure is compared to results from two different electronic structure calculations in Fig. 6 to illustrate the challenges that biomolecule structures pose for theory. In Fig. 6A, the theoretical calculation uses density functional theory (with the B3LYP functional). The comparison highlights a well-known deficiency of this theoretical approach: the lack of dispersion-type interactions to account for the interaction between the aromatic rings.⁶²⁻⁶⁴ Without these interactions, a grossly incorrect hinge angle (111°) is obtained. The second theoretical structure, shown in Fig. 6B, comes from an MP2 calculation with a large basis set and was obtained from the benchmark results web site of Hobza.^{60,65} This comparison highlights another well documented result that MP2 calculations overestimate the dispersion interaction leading, in this case, to a hinge angle smaller (48°) than experiment.⁶⁶

The dimer substitution structure has some noticeable potential deficiencies. In particular, the view chosen for the representation in Fig. 6 shows a significant non-planarity of the donor aromatic ring. Although it is difficult to glean from this view, there is also non-planarity in the acceptor ring. Closer inspection also reveals some distortion in the bond angles of the rings. These results are interesting when compared to substitution structures we have recently reported for molecules with the benzene ring. Even for molecules of comparable size and shape (such as strawberry aldehyde, $C_{12}H_{14}O_3$ and $A=1214$ MHz, $B=287$ MHz, and $C=269$ MHz for its *trans* isomer),⁶ we have not observed such significant apparent distortions in the geometry.^{54,67} This comparison suggests that a more careful examination of the use of Kraitchman analysis for heavy atom substitution in weakly bound complexes, where large amplitude motion occurs, is warranted.

2-Hydroxypyridine/2-Pyridone (2HP/2PY) Tautomers and Related FTMW Methods for Structure Determination of Biomolecules

These studies use two extensions of broadband microwave spectroscopy that may play an important role as the CP-FTMW technique is extended to large biomolecules. Proof-of-principle experiments were performed on the 2HP/2PY system shown in Fig. 7, in which a tautomeric equilibrium exists between the *enol* and *keto* forms of the same molecule. This system has been well characterized using both microwave and UV/VIS spectroscopies.⁶⁸⁻⁷² The ground state of 2HP is more stable by ~ 3 kJ/mol than that of 2PY, so both tautomers are present in appreciable concentration at room temperature. Our objective was to show that that CCPT technique could

be used to obtain tautomer-specific microwave and/or UV/VIS spectra of both species present in the sample, one at a time.

The CP-FTMW spectrum of 2HP/2PY over the frequency range 13.250-13.500 GHz is shown in Fig. 8. Clearly apparent are two strong lines in the spectrum, lying between 13.270 – 13.300 GHz. Since the rotational constants for both species are known,⁶⁹⁻⁷¹ the two observed transitions may be readily assigned as the ($J_{K_aK_c}$) 3_{03} - 2_{02} transitions of both tautomers, with the 2HP line lying some 30 MHz to the red of the corresponding 2PY line. The two tautomers also exhibit different ^{14}N nuclear quadrupole splitting patterns as is clear from the expanded view of both transitions shown in the right panel of Fig. 8. The uniqueness of these patterns also may be used to distinguish the two tautomers.⁷¹

Fig. 9 shows the CCPT spectrum of the 2HP/2PY system in two wavelength regions, 36118-36122 cm^{-1} and 29830-29833 cm^{-1} . The two spectra are very similar in overall appearance. Three major types of transitions appear in each spectrum; these are the P-, Q-, and R- branches that result from $\Delta J = -1, 0,$ and $+1$ transitions from the ground to the electronically excited state. The phase of the FID depends upon the rotational level from which the laser transition originates. By convention, transitions originating in the lower rotational level in the ground state are displayed as negative peaks, whereas those originating in the higher rotational level are displayed as positive peaks, thereby accounting for the “derivative-like” appearance of some of the lines in the spectrum. The spectra in Fig. 9 also are similar because identical rotational transitions of the two tautomers were used to detect them; this would not be the case if the connected rotational levels (or electronic transition moment orientations) of the two species were different. Still, the two spectra in Fig. 9 can be clearly distinguished on the basis of the large difference in their (electronic) origin band frequencies; for 2HP (an aromatic molecule) it is 36118.69 cm^{-1} , whereas for 2PY (not aromatic) it is 29832.30 cm^{-1} .⁶⁹

Detailed analyses of spectra of this type may be used to identify the species responsible for them, in cases where this is not known from other data. An example is shown in Fig. 10. Here, the different P, Q, and R- branch transitions that appear in the spectrum of 2HP are identified with $J_{K_aK_c}$ labels; these identify the S_1 rotational levels in which transitions from the

two connected S_0 rotational levels terminate. (Transitions originating in the lower 2_{02} level are labeled in red; transitions originating in the 3_{03} level are labeled in blue). The origin band of 2HP is an *ab*-hybrid band; hence, both $\Delta K_a = 0$, $\Delta K_c = +/- 1$ and $\Delta K_a = +/- 1$, $\Delta K_c = 0$ transitions are allowed. Thus, the first two lines in the P-branch originate in the 3_{03} level of the S_0 state, and terminate in the 2_{02} (*a*-type) and 2_{12} (*b*-type) levels of the S_1 state. Similar assignments follow from an examination of the energy level diagram in Fig. 10. Thus, as many as ten different excited state energy levels can be easily identified from a single double pulse spectrum, making it possible to determine the A, B, and C rotational constants of the excited electronic state with reasonable precision. Repeating the experiment using a different ground state microwave transition will change the patterns of lines observed, making it possible (using combination-difference methods) to determine the A, B, and C rotational constants of the excited electronic state, again with reasonable precision. These results indicate that the spectral simplification achieved using CCPT spectroscopy makes it possible to study the important structural changes and dynamics in excited electronic states that are best revealed by high-resolution spectroscopy using standard pulsed laser systems.

Discussion

We have presented new results that use Fourier transform microwave spectroscopy as the primary tool to analyze gas-phase biomolecule structure. In this section we make some comments about the future development and impact that these techniques might have in biomolecule spectroscopy and analytical chemistry more generally.

Reduced Bandwidth CP-FTMW for Biomolecule Spectroscopy

Several considerations suggest that reduced bandwidth CP-FTMW can develop into a low-cost technique for the characterization of large biomolecules. These large species, with their associated small rotational constants and dense rotational spectra, can be characterized with small spectral bandwidths. For example, the analysis of the isotopomers of the phenol dimer used a spectrum spanning just 2 GHz. As the molecules of interest get larger, the peak of the intensity distribution moves to lower frequency. This effect is problematic for cavity FTMW spectrometers because it requires the use of large mirrors that introduce several design

difficulties.⁷³⁻⁷⁵ We have recently shown that CP-FTMW spectroscopy offers excellent performance in the 2-8 GHz frequency band in a compact spectrometer design.⁷⁶⁻⁷⁷

Advances in digital electronics are providing board-level AWG and digitizer capabilities that exceed the specifications of the current reduced bandwidth systems. The future prospects of low-cost microwave power amplifiers in this band are also favorable. The development of gallium nitride (GaN) technology and the developing market for low-cost, high-power solid state amplifiers for WiMAX applications are promising drivers for the technology required in low-frequency CP-FTMW spectroscopy. Broadband GaN amplifiers with 20 W peak power covering the 2-6 GHz frequency band are already available commercially. In the low frequency range, the polarization pulse can be longer because the dephasing times are longer (determined mainly by Doppler broadening) and we have used 4 μ s pulses in our previous reports. A spectrometer covering 4 GHz of bandwidth (2-6 GHz) and using a 4 μ s pulse duration at 20 W peak power has about the same excitation efficiency as the broadband spectrometer of Fig. 1.

2D Spectroscopies for Structure Characterization

Although we have focused on the potential for structure determination by isotopic substitution in the results on the phenol dimer, there will always be a push to apply broadband rotational spectroscopy to larger systems where there is no practical way to achieve sensitivity for natural abundance isotope studies. Furthermore, the size range of these molecules will test the limits of using primarily the moments-of-inertia to make structural assignments. As an example, tautomer shifts produce small changes in the moments-of-inertia even for small molecules like the 2HP/2PY system presented here. For the most challenging systems, additional spectral characterization will likely be a necessity and laser-microwave double-resonance spectroscopy may be an important tool for gas-phase biomolecule spectroscopy.

Spectral Signatures of Novel and Reactive Species

The challenges of biomolecule structure determination help drive new spectroscopy techniques. However, there are other important structural problems where the techniques we have described are expected to have a major impact. These techniques are particularly well-suited for the characterization of highly reactive and novel species and these applications have

been driven by the field of interstellar chemistry.⁷⁸⁻⁷⁹ Broadband rotational spectroscopy is ideally suited to analyze the complex mixture of species produced by molecular beam sources of reactive species such as pulsed discharge sources.⁸⁰⁻⁸¹ The high-resolution of this technique makes it possible to obtain the microwave spectra of these molecules without the need for chromatographic separation. The “unbiased” nature of broadband spectroscopy avoids situations where the operator searches for a target compound to the exclusion of other potentially interesting species in the sample, providing they have permanent dipole moments.

In many cases, there is interest in obtaining the spectroscopic signatures of the reactive molecules in the IR or UV-VIS for detection and monitoring applications. The CCPT technique we have described uses the high resolving power of FTMW spectroscopy to isolate a single molecule in a complex mixture for spectroscopic study. A special example of where this capability is useful is in the search for molecular carriers to the famous diffuse interstellar bands (DIBs)⁸² in astronomy. A recent report made the first molecular assignment to a DIB by assigning it to the electronic spectrum of the prevalent carbene species propadienylidene ($\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{C}=\text{C}:$),⁸³ an identification that may help determine the formation route to interstellar C_{60} and C_{70} .⁸⁴⁻⁸⁵ In general, the power of present day microwave spectroscopy techniques suggest that they will become the heir to matrix isolation⁸⁶⁻⁸⁷ and helium nanodroplet⁸⁸ techniques for the characterization of novel chemical structures.

Conclusion.

Rotationally resolved spectroscopy has always held the promise of providing detailed structural information through its ability to determine the positions of atoms through isotopic substitution studies. Over the past four years we have worked to optimize the technique of chirped-pulse Fourier transform microwave spectroscopy to tackle the challenges of gas phase biomolecule structure. Molecular rotational spectroscopy of jet cooled samples provides exceptional resolution and makes it possible to analyze complex chemical mixtures without the need for chemical separation. For biomolecule spectroscopy this capability is important because the samples often contain several conformational isomers and molecular complexes. The power of this technique was illustrated by presenting the heavy atom (^{13}C and ^{18}O) structure of a molecular complex, the phenol dimer, obtained through analysis of the rotational spectra of the

isotopomers in natural abundance. Structure determination is now routine for molecules with 10-15 heavy atoms. For applications to larger molecules, we have discussed laser-microwave double-resonance techniques that can provide additional structural characterization. It is expected that these techniques will expand the range of biomolecule studies based on rotational spectroscopy in the same way that IR-UV double-resonance spectroscopy extended the scope of fluorescence spectroscopy; an advance that helped propel the field of gas phase biomolecule spectroscopy.

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Table 1. Watson A -reduction Hamiltonian parameters for phenol dimer.

	CP-FTMW	Connell <i>et al.</i> (RCS) ⁵⁸	Weichert <i>et al.</i> (RCS) ⁵⁹	Schmitt <i>et al.</i> (UV) ⁶⁰
A (MHz)	1415.32633(48)	1418.6(57)	1414.4(6)	1416.99(39)
B (MHz)	313.367093(60)	313.5(140)	313.7(8)	313.51(1)
C (MHz)	287.960317(66)	285.5(140)	287.5(7)	288.11(1)
Δ_J (kHz)	0.372342(65)			
Δ_{JK} (kHz)	-3.91817(96)			
Δ_K (kHz)	13.079(16)			
δ_J (kHz)	0.057355(29)			
δ_K (kHz)	0.7024(85)			
# lines	302			
RMS (kHz)	11.1			

Figure 1. Schematic of the CP-FTMW spectrometer operating in the 7-18 GHz bandwidth is shown. The 24 Gs/s arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) provides sufficient bandwidth to create chirped-pulses with 11 GHz of bandwidth so that simple upconversion of the AWG pulse with a single frequency phase-locked dielectric resonator oscillator (PDRO) is the only stage of pulse generation. In this work, a pulsed traveling wave tube amplifier specified at 200 W peak power (AR 200T8G18A) is used to amplified the pulse train of 10 chirped pulse used in FID collection on each sample injection. Sample is injected through two pulsed nozzle sources. For full bandwidth operation, the molecular free induction decay emission is directly digitized with a 50 Gs/s digital oscilloscope.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the reduced bandwidth CP-FTMW spectrometer.

Figure 3. Microwave pulse sequences for the CCPT experiment are illustrated. The Bloch vector for the pure rotational levels of the transition being monitored by FTMW spectroscopy is shown. The two pulse sequence creates a coherence ($\pi/2$) and then returns this to the initial population difference ($-\pi/2$). As depicted in (a), if the laser pulse is not resonant with a transition from either rotational level (i.e. no absorption), then no rotational signal is detected following the two microwave pulses. If the laser pulse is resonant with a transition out of the lower rotational level, then a population difference is created as shown in (b). In this case, the second pulse ($-\pi/2$) converts the laser-induced population difference into a coherence (along the $+y$ -direction) that is subsequently detected in the FTMW spectrometer. Panel (c) shows the case where the laser is resonant with a transition from the upper rotational level of the monitored rotational transition. Now the population component of the Bloch vector is initially along the $-z$ -direction. The second microwave pulse ($-\pi/2$) converts this laser-induced population into a coherence pointing along the $-y$ direction and it is detected with a phase opposite to that shown in (b).

Figure 4. The CP-FTMW spectrum obtained of the pulsed jet expansion of phenol (black) is dominated by the rotational transitions of the monomer at the >2 mV intensity level. However, the pure rotational spectrum of the dimer is visible at intensities of about 0.3 mV. The expanded scale in Panel B highlights a spectral region dominated by the phenol dimer spectrum. In both figures the experimental spectrum is compared to the simulated spectrum of phenol dimer at 1 K (blue).

Figure 5. Panel A shows the $14_1 14-13_1 13$ transition for phenol dimer. After a magnification of 100 (panel B), the ^{13}C isotopologue transitions can be seen at a S/N ratio of 20. The full spectrum is shown in black, while the in the blue spectrum the isotopologue transitions are isolated. Pair a is for C9 and C5, b is C10 and C4, c is C8 and C6, d is C11 and C3, e is C7 and C1, and f is C12 and C2. The red line in panel B is 1% of the intensity of the normal species transition marked in panel A showing the relative intensity accuracy obtained over a large dynamic range achieved using CP-FTMW spectroscopy. The linewidths of these transitions is ~ 130 kHz (full-width at half-height).

Figure 6. Panel A displays the substitution structure (in color) overlaid with the *ab initio* structure calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d,p). Panel B compares the experimental structure with the *ab initio* structure calculated at MP2/cc-VTZ cp (Ref. 57). For both panels the Kraitchman radii are 0.14 Å and the C atoms are colored blue while the O atoms are colored red. For the *ab initio* atoms the radii for the C are 0.23 Å, O are 0.21 Å, and H are 0.11 Å. In the r_s structure, the horizontal ring is the donor ring while the vertical ring is the acceptor ring.

Figure 7. Tautomeric equilibrium in 2-hydroxypyridine (left) and 2-pyridone (right).

Figure 8. Reduced bandwidth CP-FTMW spectra of 2HP and 2PY are shown. The spectrometer provides about 240 MHz of measurement bandwidth (left panel) in each signal acquisition. The spectrum was recorded with 1000 FID averages. The right panel shows the region of the $3_{03}-2_{02}$ rotational transitions of PY and HP with the ^{14}N nuclear quadrupole hyperfine structure.

Figure 9. CCPT spectra of the origin bands for 2HP and 2PY are shown. In this case, electronic spectroscopy provides a clear signature of the different tautomers. For both spectra, 100 signal averages were performed for each frequency step, and the laser was scanned at a speed of $3.6 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\text{hr}$.

Figure 10. The rotational assignments of the CCPT electronic spectrum of 2HP is shown with a schematic level diagram. The phase sensitive detection of CCPT provides automatic assignment of the S_0 rotational level of the transition based on the sign of the signal (see Fig. 3). The linewidth of these transitions is $\sim 0.05 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, limited by the Doppler width in the pulsed jet expansion.

Table of Contents

Broadband rotational spectroscopy has achieved performance levels that permit routine structure determination of biomolecules in the gas phase using natural abundance isotopic substitution.

